

OPERAS-P

OPEN SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION IN THE EUROPEAN
RESEARCH AREA FOR SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES -
PREPARATION

Communication, Outreach and Advocacy
Communication and Dissemination Guide

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OPEN SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION IN SSH IN THE EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA - PREPARATION

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Communication and Dissemination Guide

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I. Executive summary

The Communication and Dissemination Guide describes the communication strategy for the OPERAS-P project. It is a guideline for the dissemination and communication activities of all project partners when sharing information about the project OPERAS-P and on the research infrastructure OPERAS.

The guide identifies the core message of the project and the infrastructure to be communicated, the strategy for communication and dissemination, and describes the communication channels that the project uses. It also provides an overview of items available to all project partners for download (toolbox) and presents the editorial calendar.

The Dissemination and Communication Guide is subject to change as the project evolves and can be adapted to the project's needs.

II. Strategy

The OPERAS-P external communication strategy aims to:

1. communicate the project OPERAS-P and the acknowledgement of its EU-funding to a large audience of stakeholders and target groups.
2. promote the research infrastructure OPERAS and its mission and vision in the field of scholarly communication in SSH, its services and community.

The goals of OPERAS' communication strategy are, first, to advocate for open scholarly communication in SSH and then to encourage potential interested parties to join OPERAS. Therefore, the nature of OPERAS as a community-driven infrastructure open to the community should be reflected in its communication strategy.

The specific objectives of the communication strategy are defined in the listing of the target audiences (III b). The overall aim of the communication measures are to maintain a high public awareness of the Research Infrastructures and a positive public image. The aim is to reach a corporate reputation of the infrastructure as regards to trust, respect, reliability and credibility.

A. Infrastructure

1. Mission Statement

The mission defines the existence and the field of operation of the organisation. It communicates the purpose of OPERAS:

OPERAS is the Research Infrastructure supporting open scholarly communication in the European Research Area for the social sciences and humanities (SSH). Its mission is to coordinate and federate resources in Europe to efficiently address the scholarly communication needs of European researchers in the field of SSH.

The mission is closely connected to the vision of OPERAS:

OPERAS' aim is to make Open Science a reality for research in the SSH. We want to achieve a scholarly communication system where knowledge produced in the SSH benefits researchers, academics, and students fully and widely, and where it also benefits the whole society across Europe and worldwide.

2. Tagline

OPERAS' tagline defines the main field of OPERAS activities and is part of OPERAS' visual identity:

“open scholarly communication in the european research area for social sciences and humanities”

3. Core Messages to Communicate

The European landscape in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) is poorly integrated. The fragmentation of the scholarly communication landscape across a multitude of small-size service providers prevents the research community to transition efficiently to the open science paradigm. New digital research methods demand cutting edge scholarly communication technologies and services. On a national level, open scholarly communication in the SSH has already witnessed tremendous improvements. Yet, this development is only in the early stages on a trans-European scale, so a model for sustainable open scholarly communication in the SSH is greatly needed. OPERAS will fill this gap through

- coordination;
- adopting common standards;
- sharing research & development;
- identifying and adopting best practices;
- assessing sustainable economic models;
- advocating for OA in the SSH;
- providing seamless services at a European and international level.

4. Unique selling point

Distributed Infrastructure – OPERAS as a distributed research infrastructure will occupy a central position in the ecosystem of scholarly communication for SSH. It will coordinate the different stakeholders, i. e. researchers, research institutions, libraries, platforms, publishers and funders on their scholarly communication activities in the field of SSH.

Openness – OPERAS will introduce the principle of Open Science and ensure effective dissemination and global access to research results in the SSH.

Direct Impact – Robust services will directly enhance research outputs, particularly regarding their socio-economic impact, open access to high quality content will facilitate the research process, and sharing of technologies and knowledge will noticeably improve scholarly communication infrastructures and initiatives.

Innovation – Information and studies on the impact of evaluative methods, metric systems, new business models and sustainability strategies will serve as driver for new concepts on impact and measurement of academic merit and will influence the way research is communicated. Analyses of innovative scholarly practices and of experiences and expectations of the scholarly community will allow OPERAS to develop services that will rise up to the new ways in which research is conducted.

B. OPERAS-P

1. Project Outline

The project OPERAS-P supports the OPERAS Research Infrastructure in its development to successfully get on the ESFRI Roadmap and to become a sustainable infrastructure.

C. Branding

The aim is to use the OPERAS-P project and its logo to strengthen the branding of the infrastructure. As the main aim of the OPERAS-P project is to support the distributed research infrastructure (RI) OPERAS on its way to become a European RI, the communication strategy supports this by strengthening the brand OPERAS. As the project runs for 24 month, it would not make sense to create a completely new brand. Therefore, OPERAS-P's visual identity is based on the visual identity of the OPERAS RI that has been established in the previous OPERAS-D project. The aim here is to ensure continuity in terms of visual identity throughout OPERAS' different stages of development.

III. Target Audience

A. Stakeholder Analysis

According to the latest analysis of stakeholders, OPERAS targets eight stakeholder groups. The most important group is SSH researchers as they are the main users of the services. One stakeholder can belong to more than one group and can therefore be targeted on different levels.

The eight target groups are defined as follows:

1. SSH Researchers (under different roles: Information Seekers, Readers, Authors, Reviewers, Editors)
2. ScholComm service providers
 - 2.1. Publishers (University presses, Publishing departments in academic institutions, Library-based publishers, Scholar-led publishers, Scholarly Societies, Commercial publishers (SMEs, Bigs))
 - 2.2. Dissemination platforms and repositories (Institutional, National, International)
 - 2.3. Other digital tools and services providers (Authoring tools and services providers, Peer-reviewing tools and services providers, Copy-editing tools and services providers, Annotation tools and services providers, Marketplace tools and services, Library tools and services)
3. Research policy makers (Ministries of Research and Higher Education, Research Councils, Evaluation agencies)
4. Funders (Regional funding agencies, National funding agencies, charities and private funders, international funders)
5. Institutions (universities and RPOs), (Central administrations, Academic libraries, Research departments)
6. Infrastructures (E-infrastructures and Research Infrastructures: International, European, National, Regional)
7. Society/Socio-economic actors (journalists, associations, administrations, SMEs, “movements”, creative class, amateurs)
8. OPERAS, OPERAS-P, and TRIPLE consortia and CO-OPERAS network

B. Target Audience – dissemination measure

Target audience	Key Messages	Objectives
SSH researchers	<p>OPERAS supports SSH research and open scholarly communication</p> <p>OPERAS supports multilingual publications</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • showcase the services for researchers • address as potential user/tester of the services
Scholcomm service providers	<p>OPERAS develops services to facilitate Open Access</p> <p>You can get involved!</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • attract new members • provision of services • connect small publishers in particular
Research policy makers	<p>SSH is important</p> <p>open scholarly communication is important, especially in SSH</p> <p>As a European Research Infrastructure, OPERAS is very well integrated in the scholarly communication and EOSC landscape</p> <p>OPERAS' necessity has been proven by demand from researchers and other stakeholders</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • convince decision makers and receive political support • prove the benefits and the necessity of OPERAS to the European research landscape • maintain and increase support from current member states • attract new member states • promote public interest in SSH research
Funders	<p>Open scholarly communication infrastructures must be funded in a consistent way</p> <p>OPERAS is the Research Infrastructure supporting open scholarly communication</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • receive funding

	<p>OPERAS' mission is to coordinate and federate resources in Europe to efficiently address the scholarly communication needs of European researchers in the field of SSH</p>	
Institutions (including libraries)	<p>OPERAS develops services to facilitate Open Access</p> <p>OPERAS supports and facilitates networking in the field of SSH and open scholarly communication</p> <p>OPERAS is active in the field of SSH research</p> <p>You can get involved!</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● attract potential members ● provision of services ● gain greater visibility as an important Research Infrastructure for the SSH
Infrastructures	<p>OPERAS is the Research Infrastructure supporting open scholarly communication</p> <p>OPERAS is a getaway for the SSH scholarly communication community to the EOSC</p> <p>OPERAS aims at collaborating with other infrastructures and does not intend to duplicate services or areas of activities</p> <p>You can get involved!</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● prove the benefits and the necessity of OPERAS to the European research landscape ● provision of services
Society/Socio-economic actors	<p>OPERAS supports and facilitates networking with other socio-economic actors and SSH research (data, publications, researchers)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● find SSH research and multiply/work with it for a broader audience ● promote public interest in SSH research

	OPERAS is the European Research Infrastructure opening the access to SSH research	
OPERAS, OPERAS-P, and TRIPLE consortia and CO-OPERAS network	OPERAS addresses different stakeholders differently	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ensure an efficient sharing of information across the different groups • support multilingualism

Target audience	Means of dissemination		
	Publications and other dissemination material	OPERAS-P events	Communication channels
SSH Researchers	Scientific articles, Special Interest Group book	International conferences, OPERAS services workshops	Social media, blog, video series, flyer
Scholcomm service providers (publishers, publishing platforms)	Scientific articles, Advocacy Guide, Landscape Study, Special Interest Group book	International conferences, advocacy workshop, national node workshop, OPERAS services workshops	Social media, website, blog, newsletter, video series, flyer, position papers
Scholcomm service providers (libraries, infrastructure providers)	Advocacy Guide, Landscape Study, Special Interest Group book	International conferences, advocacy workshop, national node workshop, OPERAS services workshops	Social media, website, blog, newsletter, video series, flyer, position papers
Institutions	Scientific articles, Advocacy Guide, Special Interest Group	International conferences, advocacy workshop,	Social media, website, blog, newsletter, video

	book	national node workshop, OPERAS services workshops	series, flyer, position papers
Infrastructures	Scientific articles, Advocacy Guide, Landscape Study, Networking Report, Special Interest Group book, Handbook for National Nodes	International conferences, OPERAS services workshops	Social media, website, blog, newsletter, video series, policy briefs, position papers
Research policy makers	Special Interest Group book, handbook for National Nodes	International conferences, national node workshop	website, newsletter, policy briefs, position papers
Society/Socio-economic actors	Scientific articles, Special Interest Group book	International conferences, national node workshop	website, social media, blog, video series, position papers
OPERAS-P and OPERAS consortium	Scientific articles, Advocacy Guide, Landscape Study, Special Interest Group book, project deliverables, handbook for National Nodes	International conferences, advocacy workshops, national node workshop, OPERAS services workshops	Social media, website, blog, newsletter, video series, policy briefs, position papers
Funders	Scientific articles, Landscape Study, Special Interest Group book, handbook for National Nodes	International conferences, advocacy workshops, OPERAS services workshops	Social media, website, blog, newsletter, video series, policy briefs, position papers

C. Potential risks

1. Stakeholders can experience OPERAS as a “closed club”.

Reaction: There are several direct links on the website to invite people to get involved and to become a member. All the participation rules, governance structure, application procedures are transparent and made publicly available.

2. Potential new members can not see the benefit of OPERAS as long as the services are not yet available.

Reaction: Communication measures to show all activities OPERAS is already performing for the benefit of the different targeting groups.

IV. Internal Communication OPERAS

Several measures have been implemented to organize the work for the infrastructure OPERAS and to organize and facilitate the internal communication. Apart from several face-to-face and virtual meetings and the OPERAS events, the internal communication is organized by means of different communication tools. Mattermost, a collaboration software, and Trello, a project management software, are open source. Therefore, they can easily be expanded to include new members of the growing infrastructure.

Mattermost: There are chat groups for the different OPERAS Special Interest Groups to discuss tasks and activities.

Zoom: There are regularly video conferences via zoom for the different work packages. The regular meetings are documented in minutes that every participant of the project can access via a cloud.

Trello: The management tool is used to organize the work for the infrastructure. For every project is a Trello-Board installed to manage the work within the projects, and there is a special Trello-Board for the preparation of the ESFRI application. The OPERAS Coordination organizes their work within an own Trello Board. Links to relevant documents in the shared cloud are made in the respective Trello-cards. Therefore, all participants have an up-to-date overview of the current status of the different tasks and can access the linked documents.

V. Communication Channels

A. OPERAS Website

The OPERAS website is the main communication channel of the infrastructure. All projects of the infrastructure are presented on this website. OPERAS-P deliverables as well as the

deliverables from other OPERAS projects are listed and highlighted on the OPERAS website and disseminated via Zenodo.

B. OPERAS Blog

Currently, the blog at hypotheses <https://operas.hypotheses.org/> is used as a website. After the migration of the new portal to Unito (host), the current website will remain as a blog where all news are pronounced and detailed blog posts are published. The new website hosted by UniTo will serve as the infrastructure website including the introduction of the different projects, services, international partnerships and an event calendar.

The advantage of running a blog with its own URL on the Hypotheses platform, in addition to the website, is that it is easier to expand the target audience than if the blog was embedded in the OPERAS website. Hypotheses offers a lot of community work within the research community. OPERAS can use this expanded target audience to reach more people with its communication work.

Ideas for new blog series are:

Therefore, a restructuring into an OPERAS blog with several blog series is necessary. Planned series are:

- OPERAS news
- OPERAS community (Report on interesting events and happenings in the community)
- OPERAS Behind the Scenes? (Introducing people working for OPERAS, developing services ...)

C. Social Media Channels (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn)

The activity in social media channels facilitates a two-way conversation and enables the project to reach a broader audience than through more traditional dissemination activities. OPERAS' social media strategy focuses on community building and networking. It is intended that all OPERAS partners take an active part in the conversations, and they are encouraged to use #OPERAS and @OPERASEU for relevant posts on their own social media channels. All social media accounts are administered and maintained by MWS.

The social media channels, especially Twitter, are used to inform the OPERAS community and to reach a growing audience and to show the OPERAS community.

Twitter: @OPERASEU is the most important channel to reach the target audiences. Although the main language is English, we motivate our members to retweet our tweets

with a comment in their native language and to tag @OPERASEU in conversations in their native community with an English comment to emphasise OPERAS' multilingual approach.

The goals of the Twitter presence of OPERAS are to:

- Build a strong base of engaged followers
- Gain more attention for the OPERAS community
- Drive more traffic to the OPERAS blog and website
- Engage with user communities/Respond to queries
- Monitor and improve OPERAS' reputation

Tweets are mainly made about:

- Tweets to introduce the partners
- Tweets on blog posts
- Tweets on events attended/speeches
- Tweets on publications/research results
- Retweet of posts to show the community and their activities

The channels Facebook and LinkedIn are mainly used to spread news about OPERAS. For this purpose, the Twitter posts can be modified and send through these channels as well. They reach those parts of the target audience who use channels other than Twitter.

D. Newsletter

A GDPR compliant e-newsletter will be disseminated in English on a regular basis (every 2-3 months, starting January 2020), informing key stakeholders of project developments. Registration to the e-newsletter is open to the interested public and is advertised on the project website and through social media channels.

E. Dissemination

For the dissemination of the OPERAS-P deliverables and the OPERAS publications a Zenodo community has been established. All public deliverables are being uploaded here to receive a permanent identifier DOI and to be published sustainably. The community: "OPERAS: open scholarly communication in the European research area for social sciences and humanities" with the identifier "operaseu" is used for all OPERAS publications, as well for completed projects such as OPERAS-D and HIRMEOS. The Zenodo community will be directly linked on the OPERAS website, www.operas-eu.org.

F. Event Calendar

Several events are planned as part of the project to assemble different stakeholder groups, to develop together and communicate the different aims in the project. Therefore, different event formats have been developed. All events will be accompanied by communication efforts and will be announced through the media channels.

Currently planned events:

When	What	Organizing Institution	Channels to Communicate	Main Communication Aim
1–2 October 2019	OPERAS-P Kick-off Meeting	IBL-Pan	Website, Twitter, E-Mail	Introduce the project and OPERAS
February 2020	DOAB Workshop for researchers	DOAB	Website, Twitter	Raise awareness around OA books
Mai 2020	Workshop Innovative Governance Models	Uni Lu	Website, Twitter, E-Mail	
Spring 2020	Advocacy Workshop	Unito	Website, Twitter, E-Mail	Advocacy for researchers at libraries and infrastructure providers
3-5 June 2020	OPERAS Annual Conference	MWS	several campaigns Website, Twitter, Facebook, Linked-In, E-Mail, Face-to-face	Gain attention for OPERAS and its aims, connect the community
Summer 2020	DOAB Workshop for Librarians	DOAB	Website, Twitter	Raise awareness around OA books
October 2020	Workshop Standard Mapping	OpenEdition	Website, Twitter, E-Mail	
November 2020	Advocacy Workshop for Researchers	MWS	Website, Twitter, E-Mail	Advocacy for researchers with universities and research organizations
December	Advocacy	Coimbra	Website, Twitter,	Advocacy for

2020	Workshop for		E-Mail	researchers with publishers
March 2021	National Node Workshop' Greece	EKT	Website, Twitter, LinkedIn, e-newsletter	Introduce OPERAS to national communities
March 2021	National Nodes Workshop: Germany	MWS	Website, Twitter, E-Mail	Introduce OPERAS to national communities
	National Nodes Workshop: France	CNRS	Website, Twitter, E-Mail	Introduce OPERAS to national communities
	National Nodes Workshop: Netherlands	OAPEN	Website, Twitter, E-Mail	Introduce OPERAS to national communities
May 2021	National Nodes Workshop: Poland	IBL-Pan	Website, Twitter, E-Mail	Introduce OPERAS to national communities
	National Nodes Workshop: Croatia	University of Zadar	Website, Twitter, E-Mail	Introduce OPERAS to national communities
	National Nodes Workshop: Italy	UniTo	Website, Twitter, E-Mail	Introduce OPERAS to national communities
June 2021	OPERAS Annual Conference "Future of OPERAS"	IBL-Pan	several campaigns Website, Twitter, Facebook, Linked-In, E-Mail, Face-to-face	Gain attention for OPERAS and its aims, connect the community

VI. Communication Toolbox and Assets

The following visual materials are subject to change as the project and infrastructure evolve. They will be updated regularly.

A. Visual Identity

1. Infrastructure

The visual identity for the infrastructure has been prepared by the design agency “Oktober Kommunikationsdesign” (<http://oktober.de/>). The logo has been approved by the Steering Committee on 11 April 2017. The Core Group decided in June 2020 to change the tagline of the OPERAS RI to “*open scholarly communication in the european research area for social sciences and humanities*”. Therefore, the logo has been adapted as part of the project.

Colors:

A color scheme defining two primary and two secondary colors

primary color “red”: 170/10/45, #AA0A2D

primary color “purple”: 105/35/100, #692364

secondary color “black”: 0/0/0, #000000

secondary color “grey”: 135/135/135, #878787

Logo Infrastructure:

The toolbox is providing the logo in different formats (eps, jpg web and print format, pdf).

Logo with tagline:

OPERAS

open scholarly communication in the european
research area for social sciences and humanities

A web banner with tagline:

2. Project OPERAS-P

The OPERAS-P project uses the visual identity as the infrastructure but has its own logo dedicated to the project's name:

OPERAS-P

B. Template for Presentations

Basic templates for presentations have been developed and are available (.pptx) in the toolbox: one template for all presentations of the infrastructure and one for all events in context of the project. All stakeholders are free to add their own logo to these templates.

1. Infrastructure

2. OPERAS-P Project

C. Presence at Conferences

All participants in the project are taking part in international conferences according to the OPERAS aims and are presenting the infrastructure and the work done in the project. To present the infrastructure, individual posters are created and published under a CC-licence. All conference speeches, panels, poster presentations are accompanied by twitter campaigns. Conference attendances are proposed via the twitter channel and are accompanied by tweets and retweets in the official channel and member accounts.

D. Other Promotional Material

Other texts and promotional materials, e.g. articles, reports, videos and an updated poster will be developed further on in the project if the need arises, and they will also be made available on the project website.

Beneficiaries of the EU's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme have the

obligation to explicitly acknowledge that their action has received EU funding in all communication, dissemination and IPR activities as well as on all equipment, infrastructure and major results funded by the grant. The following statement, which is available in high resolution and in different formats (square or wide format, with frame or without, with transparent or white background, in jpg) in the toolbox and on the website, needs to be included on all activities within the project OPERAS-P mentioned above.

Funding Information

Infrastructure

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OPERAS-P Project

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Please note that the EU emblem should be used for all communication and dissemination activities (not the logo of the European Commission):

VII. Appendix

- VIII. OPERAS Design Manual
- IX. OPERAS Flyer

X. Dissemination level

PU = Public

